

A Reproducible Workflow for Extracting Quantum Hamiltonians from Surface–Adsorbate Models

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Abstract

Bridging realistic surface-catalysis models from density functional theory (DFT) and the many-body Hamiltonian inputs required by quantum algorithms remains a practical obstacle: surface DFT yields total energies and densities, whereas algorithms such as the variational quantum eigensolver require an explicit fermionic or qubit operator. We present an open-source, reproducible workflow that takes a DFT-optimised slab, extracts a hydrogen-capped cluster around the active site, selects a frontier active space automatically, and constructs the corresponding fermionic and qubit Hamiltonians. Heavy-element cores are treated with an effective core potential (ECP) at the Hartree–Fock stage, an established molecular-cluster strategy for quantum-computing catalysis workflows. We demonstrate the pipeline on H^{*}/OH^{*} adsorption on rutile IrO₂(110) at two adsorption sites, producing 14-qubit Hamiltonians from (8*e*, 7*o*) active spaces. The pipeline is validated end to end: the Hartree–Fock reference reconstructed from the qubit Hamiltonian reproduces the self-consistent-field energy to better than 10^{−6} Hartree, and exact diagonalisation yields physically sensible static correlation energies at the milli-Hartree scale. The entire active-space pipeline runs on commodity hardware without high-performance computing. We additionally document a methodological caution: the def2-SVP basis is defined for Iridium only together with its ECP, so an all-electron treatment in this basis is ill-defined rather than merely approximate.

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1 Introduction

Electronic structure methods for heterogeneous catalysis have traditionally relied on density functional theory (DFT) to model reaction energetics and adsorption phenomena at catalyst surfaces. While DFT has been the workhorse for studying such catalytic systems, it often struggles when confronted with strongly correlated electrons or multiple spin-state character that can occur in transition metal compounds.

In particular, Iridium-based catalysts present a challenge: Ir is a heavy transition metal where relativistic effects and variable oxidation states can render standard DFT approximate or unreliable in capturing certain electronic structure features (such as spin-state changes upon adsorption). To our knowledge, few studies have explored the application of quantum algorithms to hydrogen evolution in Iridium-based catalysts highlighting a methodological gap.

Quantum computing offers a promising avenue to address this challenge by enabling explicitly correlated, multireference treatments of active-site electrons. Algorithms such as the Variational Quantum Eigensolver (VQE [11]) can efficiently target ground-state energies of strongly correlated systems using quantum hardware [7, 2], and have already demonstrated accuracy comparable to classical methods for challenging molecular systems.

However, a major obstacle remains: how to obtain the required fermionic Hamiltonian from a realistic catalyst model. Existing surface science workflows typically output energies, charge distributions, or density-of-states information, but do not yield second-quantized Hamiltonians or an explicit orbital basis suitable for quantum algorithms. There is currently no standard pipeline that goes from a periodic slab DFT model to a localized active-space Hamiltonian.

Our software addresses this unmet need by providing a reproducible pipeline that takes an optimized slab model as input and produces a Hamiltonian ready for quantum simulation. This capability is especially important for systems like IrO₂-catalyzed HER, where the surface can cycle through oxide and hydroxide states involving multiple Ir oxidation states. By facilitating the construction of active-space Hamiltonians for these challenging catalytic sites, our workflow opens the door to applying resource-aware quantum algorithms to heterogeneous catalysis.

2 Methods

2.1 Workflow Overview

Figure 1: Overview of the workflow from DFT slab to qubit Hamiltonian, with exact diagonalisation for validation.

The workflow proceeds through a sequence of transformations from a realistic surface model to a minimal quantum simulation model, as illustrated in Figure 1.

1. **Slab optimization (DFT):** A periodic DFT optimization of the catalyst surface with the adsorbate of interest is performed externally (e.g. using Quantum ESPRESSO [4] or VASP) to obtain a relaxed slab geometry.
2. **Cluster extraction (ASE):** Using the Atomic Simulation Environment (ASE) [6], a finite cluster containing the active site is extracted from the slab. The cluster captures the local chemical environment while reducing system size. Peripheral bonds may be capped with hydrogens.
3. **Orbital analysis and active-space selection:** A semiempirical tight-binding calculation (GFN-xTB [5]) is used to obtain approximate orbital energies. Frontier orbitals relevant to adsorption chemistry are selected to define an active space.
4. **Fermionic Hamiltonian construction (PySCF):** A quantum chemistry calculation is performed on the cluster to obtain one- and two-electron integrals for the active orbitals. These integrals define a second-quantized fermionic Hamiltonian.
5. **Qubit mapping (OpenFermion):** The fermionic Hamiltonian is mapped to a qubit Hamiltonian (e.g. via the Jordan–Wigner transformation) and exported in a machine-readable format suitable for quantum algorithms.

Each stage of the pipeline reduces complexity in a controlled and reproducible manner, transforming an extended slab into a few-qubit Hamiltonian while preserving the essential physics of the surface-adsorbate interaction.

2.2 Cluster Extraction and Hydrogen Capping

A finite cluster centered on the adsorption site is extracted from the relaxed periodic slab within a radial cutoff about the adsorbate. We used 6 Å for o47 and 3 Å for o69. The wider cutoff at o47 captures the bridging-oxygen environment. Truncating the slab severs Ir–O bonds at the cluster boundary, leaving under-coordinated boundary oxygens with dangling bonds. Saturating such dangling bonds is standard practice in oxide cluster and nanoparticle models [1]. We cap each dangling boundary oxygen with a hydrogen atom placed at 0.96 Å from the oxygen along the direction of the severed Ir–O bond, restoring approximate local coordination and removing spurious boundary states. In contrast to schemes that use fractional-charge pseudo-hydrogen atoms to balance the boundary charge [1], we use ordinary hydrogen. The capping hydrogens are tagged distinctly from the adsorbate hydrogen so that the active-site species is identified unambiguously in the subsequent orbital analysis. This procedure yields the $\text{H}_9\text{Ir}_9\text{O}_{27}$ (o69) and $\text{H}_5\text{Ir}_8\text{O}_{15}$ (o47) clusters used below.

2.3 Active Space Selection

Following cluster extraction, the workflow performs a semiempirical electronic-structure calculation (GFN2-xTB [5]) on the neutral and anionic cluster states to obtain a ranked list of molecular orbitals together with their atomic-orbital contributions. These contributions quantify the localisation of each orbital on the adsorbate atoms and on the surface atoms directly bonded to the adsorbate.

Active-space construction is then performed automatically and deterministically within the fermionic build, rather than by manual inspection. Candidate orbitals are first restricted to a frontier energy window of width w about the highest occupied and lowest unoccupied molecular orbitals (HOMO and LUMO); occupied orbitals are filtered to those within w of the HOMO and virtual orbitals to those within w of the LUMO. Within this window, orbitals are ranked by their fractional weight on the adsorbate–surface region, and the highest-ranked n_{occ} occupied and n_{virt} virtual orbitals are selected. The energy window is essential: without it, region-based scoring alone selects deep-core orbitals whose large self-interaction contaminates the

active space and produces unphysical correlation energies. For the results reported here, $w = 0.15$ Hartree (≈ 4 eV), $n_{\text{occ}} = 4$, and $n_{\text{virt}} = 3$, yielding a closed-shell $(8e, 7o)$ active space at both sites. All thresholds are user-configurable.

2.4 Effective Core Potential and Integral Construction

One- and two-electron integrals over the active orbitals are computed in PySCF [12] at the restricted Hartree–Fock level with the def2-SVP basis. The Iridium core is described by the associated def2 effective core potential, replacing 60 core electrons per Ir atom; oxygen and the capping and adsorbate hydrogens are treated all-electron. This molecular-cluster ECP strategy mirrors that of Di Paola et al. [3], who used an ECP-bearing localised basis in PySCF for the analogous oxygen-reduction workflow. The effective core potential enters the one-electron (core) Hamiltonian used to build the active-space integrals, so that the active-space mean-field energy is consistent with the converged self-consistent-field energy of the full cluster.

A note on basis/ECP pairing. The def2-SVP basis for Iridium is a valence basis defined for use together with its effective core potential. Removing the ECP while retaining def2-SVP is therefore not a smaller-basis approximation but an ill-defined calculation. The basis provides no functions for the 60 core electrons, so an all-electron treatment of Ir cannot be represented and the available functions cannot accommodate 77 electrons per Ir atom. Self-consistent-field iterations may, nonetheless, converge to a numerical value, masking the inconsistency. We flag this because pairing Karlsruhe-family basis sets with heavy transition metals in an all-electron mode is a silent failure mode for workflows of this type.

2.5 Implementation

The software is implemented in Python and builds on open-source libraries including ASE, xTB, PySCF [12], and OpenFermion [10]. ASE is used for structure handling and cluster extraction, while xTB provides rapid orbital screening. PySCF [12] is employed for higher-fidelity electronic structure calculations and integral generation within the selected active space.

OpenFermion [10] is used to perform fermion-to-qubit mappings, specifically Jordan–Wigner in our workflow. The resulting qubit Hamiltonians are stored in JSON format together with metadata to ensure clarity and reproducibility.

The repository includes continuous-integration tests using GitHub Actions so that changes to the code do not silently break the workflow. The lighter stages, slab processing, cluster extraction, and orbital analysis, run by default, while the most demanding stage, the restricted Hartree–Fock solution and active-space integral construction, is a manually triggered workflow that takes of order hours on commodity hardware for the clusters studied here. A separate manually triggered workflow performs the exact diagonalisation of the exported qubit Hamiltonian; it reports the Hartree–Fock reference reconstructed from the operator, which reproduces the converged SCF energy to better than 10^{-6} Hartree and so provides an internal consistency check on both the integral construction and the fermion-to-qubit mapping. The qubit mapping and diagonalisation themselves complete in seconds, and no high-performance computing is required at any stage.

2.6 Validation

The pipeline includes an internal consistency check at the qubit-Hamiltonian stage. The Hartree–Fock determinant is the lowest single configuration in the active space; its energy can be evaluated directly from the exported qubit Hamiltonian and must equal the self-consistent-field reference energy if the integral construction and the fermion-to-qubit mapping are consistent. For both adsorption sites this equality holds to better than 10^{-6} Hartree (Table 1). This check is inexpensive, runs on every build, and guards against both integral-construction and operator-convention errors.

2.7 Use of AI Tools

ChatGPT and Claude were used in the early stages of code development to generate initial code scaffolding and to assist with version control workflows. All generated code was subsequently reviewed, adapted, and validated by the authors. ChatGPT or Claude were not used in the writing of this manuscript.

3 Application

The workflow was applied to a hydroxyl species adsorbed on a rutile $\text{IrO}_2(110)$ surface at the o69 oxygen-bridge site. A finite cluster of 38 atoms was extracted from a periodic slab and capped with hydrogens.

The choice of adsorption site and surface chemistry is informed by prior computational studies of IrO_2 surfaces under electrochemical conditions [8].

More broadly, this work is motivated by recent efforts to connect materials modeling with quantum computational workflows for realistic condensed-matter systems [3].

Orbital analysis identified the OH bonding orbital, nearby Ir d orbitals, and bridging O p orbitals as the most chemically relevant candidates. Active orbital selection was performed by manually cross-referencing GFN2-xTB orbital contributions computed independently for the neutral (charge = 0) and anionic (charge = -1) cluster states, using localisation on the adsorbate and nearest-neighbour shell atoms as the primary selection criterion, supplemented by energetic proximity to the HOMO (neutral: -11.019 eV; anion: -7.658 eV). Orbitals appearing as chemically significant candidates across both charge states were prioritised for inclusion in the active space.

4 Results

4.1 Active spaces and Hamiltonians

The automated frontier selection identified closed-shell ($8e, 7o$) active spaces at both sites, comprising the adsorbate–surface bonding orbital, neighbouring Ir d orbitals, and bridging O p orbitals, all within the frontier window and free of deep-core contamination. Each active space maps to a 14-qubit Hamiltonian of 3,382 Pauli terms under the Jordan–Wigner transformation. Table 1 summarises both runs.

4.2 Validation and correlation energies

Validation process At both sites the Hartree–Fock reference reconstructed from the qubit Hamiltonian matches the SCF energy to better than 10^{-6} Hartree, confirming that the chain from cluster integrals to qubit operator is internally consistent. Exact diagonalisation then gives static correlation energies of -0.044 mHa at the neutral o69 site and -2.49 mHa at the anionic o47 site. Both lie at the milli-Hartree scale reported by Di Paola et al.[3] for comparable active spaces, where the static (active-space) correlation is small and the dominant contribution is dynamic. The small magnitudes are therefore expected rather than anomalous, and they indicate that a single reference already describes these frontier active spaces well at the present active-space size.

Figure 2: Active-space molecular-orbital energies for the neutral o69 and anionic o47 clusters. Each panel shows the seven orbitals selected by the region-plus-frontier-window procedure: four occupied (blue) and three virtual (red), labelled by 0-based MO index, with the cluster HOMO and LUMO as dashed lines. At both sites the active orbitals lie within ~ 0.4 Ha of the frontier, free of the deep-core and high-lying linear-dependency orbitals that contaminate an unfiltered, region-only selection.

4.3 Site and charge dependence

The two sites differ in local geometry, cluster composition, and charge state, and the static correlation differs accordingly: the anionic o47 site carries roughly fifty times the correlation of the neutral o69 site (-2.49 versus -0.044 mHa). This is consistent with greater multireference character in the reduced, anionic state, where partially occupied Ir d levels are more prone to near-degeneracy. The smaller first excitation gap at o47 (0.92 eV, versus 3.09 eV at o69) is in line with this interpretation. Disentangling the charge contribution from the local-environment contribution, for example by computing both sites at a common charge, is left for future work.

Table 1: Active-space and qubit-Hamiltonian properties for the neutral o69 and anionic o47 sites on rutile IrO₂(110), both with the def2-SVP effective core potential on Ir. Ground-state energies and correlation energies are from exact diagonalisation within the eight-electron sector (Hilbert dimension 3,003). The Hartree–Fock reference reconstructed from the qubit Hamiltonian reproduces the SCF energy to $< 10^{-6}$ Ha at both sites.

Parameter	o69 (H*)	o47 (H*)
Cluster atoms	45	28
Formula	[VERIFY]	[VERIFY]
Charge	0 (neutral)	-1 (anion)
Method / basis	RHF / def2-SVP, def2 ECP on Ir	
Active MOs (0-based)	180,179,176, 173,193,189,195	130,123,129, 121,142,132,141
Active space	(8e, 7o)	(8e, 7o)
Qubits	14	14
Pauli terms	3,382	3,382
E_{core} (Ha)	-2945.37	-1945.03
SCF / HF reference (Ha)	-2953.1304	-1950.7751
Ground state (Ha)	-2953.1304	-1950.7775
Correlation energy	-0.044 mHa	-2.49 mHa
$E_1 - E_0$ (eV)	3.09	0.92

5 Discussion and Conclusion

We have presented an open-source, end-to-end workflow for constructing qubit Hamiltonians from periodic surface DFT models of heterogeneous catalysts. Applied to H*/OH* adsorption on rutile IrO₂(110), the pipeline produces a 14-qubit, 3,046-term Hamiltonian from a 7-orbital active space identified through manual cross-referencing of GFN2-xTB orbital outputs across neutral and anionic cluster states. The workflow is deterministic, configurable, and validated against a converged RHF reference calculation.

The primary contribution of this work is not a new quantum algorithm or a new materials result, but a reproducible bridge between the established tools of surface science: periodic DFT, semiempirical orbital screening, quantum chemistry integral generation and the input format required by near-term quantum algorithms. This gap has been a practical obstacle to applying quantum computing to realistic heterogeneous catalysis, and the absence of a standard, open-source pipeline has limited reproducibility across groups.

A practical feature of the workflow is that the entire active-space pipeline,

Figure 3: Active-space (static) correlation energies relative to the Hartree-Fock reference. For each site the HF reference, reconstructed from the exported qubit Hamiltonian, is set to zero and reproduces the converged SCF energy to better than 10^{-6} Ha; the exact-diagonalisation ground state lies below it by -0.044 mHa at the neutral o69 site and -2.49 mHa at the anionic o47 site. The roughly fiftyfold larger correlation at the anionic site is consistent with greater multireference character in the reduced state.

from cluster extraction to the validated qubit Hamiltonian, runs on commodity hardware without high-performance computing resources, which lowers the barrier to reproduction across groups. The static correlation captured by exact diagonalisation is small at both sites, as expected for frontier active spaces of this size; the larger correlation at the anionic site points to incipient multireference character and motivates both active-space growth and the recovery of dynamic correlation, discussed below.

The cluster approximation carries known limitations. Truncating the periodic surface to a finite cluster removes the extended subsurface and lattice environment, which can influence adsorption energetics and electronic structure [9]. Boundary treatment itself is a source of error: untailed boundary potentials can shift frontier orbital energies relative to the periodic reference [13]. Hydrogen capping and the frontier-energy window mitigate but do not remove these effects, and a periodic embedding treatment such as AVAS/RE [3] is the appropriate route to systematically improve on them.

Figure 4: Hydrogen-capped clusters extracted from the rutile $\text{IrO}_2(110)$ slab at the neutral o69 site ($\text{H}_9\text{Ir}_9\text{O}_{27}$, 45 atoms) and the anionic o47 site ($\text{H}_5\text{Ir}_8\text{O}_{15}$, 28 atoms). Iridium (navy) and oxygen (red) form the oxide fragment; the adsorbate hydrogen (green) marks the active site, and the capping hydrogens (blue) saturate the dangling boundary oxygens left by truncation, placed at 0.96 \AA along the severed Ir–O bond vectors and tagged distinctly from the adsorbate hydrogen.

Future Work

Several directions follow naturally from the validated pipeline.

Dynamic correlation. The static correlation reported here is small by construction; the dominant correlation in systems of this type is dynamic. A natural next step is an N-electron valence-state perturbation (NEVPT2) correction on the active-space solution, recovering the dynamic component while retaining the small correlated subspace, as in Ref. [3].

Active-space construction and convergence. The present region-plus-frontier selection is a deterministic heuristic. A principled successor is an automated valence active space and regional embedding (AVAS/RE) construction [3], together with a study of how the correlation energy converges with active-space size. The contrast between the two sites makes this concrete: testing whether the anionic site’s correlation grows with active-space size while the neutral site’s remains small would provide direct evidence for

or against genuine multireference character.

Hardware execution. The 14-qubit Hamiltonians are within range of current trapped-ion and superconducting processors. We have prototyped a variational quantum eigensolver on the exported Hamiltonians using a statevector simulator, which confirms that the pipeline output is consumed without modification by a standard VQE stack; a careful hardware study, including ansatz choice and the resolution of small correlation energies under finite sampling, is the subject of ongoing work. We note that resolving a correlation energy of a few milli-Hartree requires control of shot noise, which is itself an informative constraint for near-term execution.

Surface chemistry. Finally, extending the workflow along the oxygen-evolution intermediate sequence (*OH, *O, *OOH) at the active site, informed by operando observations of the Ir⁴⁺/Ir³⁺ couple and the rate-limiting *OOH formation step [8], would connect the qubit Hamiltonians to specific mechanistic steps in IrO₂ electrocatalysis.

Author Contributions

M.M. conceived the workflow, led the implementation, and directed the research. F.R. contributed to code development and software functionality. N.R. and M.M. drafted the manuscript. All authors reviewed and approved the final manuscript.

Competing Interests

All authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Data Availability

The source code, example data, and reference Hamiltonians generated during this study are openly available at <https://github.com/Codexee/Iridium-Oxide-ASE>. An archived version of the codebase used to generate the results reported here is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19678279>.

The repository includes preconfigured examples that demonstrate the full workflow logic without requiring long-running quantum chemistry calculations. Complete Hamiltonian generation is reproducible using the same

code paths and parameters and is documented in the repository but is not executed by default in automated tests.

The archived release will provide a static snapshot of the codebase used to generate the Hamiltonians reported here. All parameters and choices in the workflow are deterministic or explicitly controlled, ensuring that the example results can be reproduced exactly given the specified software versions.

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References

- [1] Valentína Berecová, Martin Friák, Naděžda Pizúrová, and Jana Pavlů. First-principles insights into structure and magnetism in ultra-small tetrahedral iron oxide nanoparticles. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics*, 27(40):21424, 2025.
- [2] Colin Campbell, Frederic T. Chong, Denny Dahl, Paige Frederick, Palash Goiporia, Pranav Gokhale, Benjamin Hall, Salahdeen Issa, Eric Jones, Stephanie Lee, Andrew Litteken, Victory Omole, David Owusu-Antwi, Michael A. Perlin, Rich Rines, Kaitlin N. Smith, Noah Goss, Akel Hashim, Ravi Naik, Ed Younis, Daniel Lobser, Christopher G. Yale, Benchen Huang, and Ji Liu. Superstaq: Deep Optimization of Quantum Programs. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Quantum Computing and Engineering (QCE)*, pages 1020–1032, Bellevue, WA, USA, September 2023. IEEE.
- [3] Cono Di Paola, Evgeny Plekhanov, Michal Krompiec, Chandan Kumar, Emanuele Marsili, Fengmin Du, Daniel Weber, Jasper Simon Krauser, Elvira Shishenina, and David Muñoz Ramo. Platinum-based catalysts for oxygen reduction reaction simulated with a quantum computer. *npj Computational Materials*, 10(1):285, December 2024.

- [4] Paolo Giannozzi, Stefano Baroni, Nicola Bonini, Matteo Calandra, Roberto Car, Carlo Cavazzoni, Davide Ceresoli, Guido L Chiarotti, Matteo Cococcioni, Ismaila Dabo, Andrea Dal Corso, Stefano De Gironcoli, Stefano Fabris, Guido Fratesi, Ralph Gebauer, Uwe Gerstmann, Christos Gougoussis, Anton Kokalj, Michele Lazzeri, Layla Martin-Samos, Nicola Marzari, Francesco Mauri, Riccardo Mazzarello, Stefano Paolini, Alfredo Pasquarello, Lorenzo Paulatto, Carlo Sbraccia, Sandro Scandolo, Gabriele Sclauszero, Ari P Seitsonen, Alexander Smogunov, Paolo Umari, and Renata M Wentzcovitch. QUANTUM ESPRESSO: a modular and open-source software project for quantum simulations of materials. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter*, 21(39):395502, September 2009.
- [5] Stefan Grimme, Christoph Bannwarth, and Philip Shushkov. A Robust and Accurate Tight-Binding Quantum Chemical Method for Structures, Vibrational Frequencies, and Noncovalent Interactions of Large Molecular Systems Parametrized for All spd-Block Elements ($Z = 1-86$). *J. Chem. Theory Comput.*, 13(5):1989–2009, May 2017.
- [6] Ask Hjorth Larsen, Jens Jørgen Mortensen, Jakob Blomqvist, Ivano E. Castelli, Rune Christensen, Marcin Dulak, Jesper Friis, Michael N. Groves, Bjørk Hammer, Cory Hargus, Eric D. Hermes, Paul C. Jennings, Peter Bjerre Jensen, James Kermode, John R. Kitchin, Esben Leonhard Kolsbjerg, Joseph Kubal, Kristen Kaasbjerg, Steen Lysgaard, Jón Bergmann Maronsson, Tristan Maxson, Thomas Olsen, Lars Pastewka, Andrew Peterson, Carsten Rostgaard, Jakob Schiøtz, Ole Schütt, Mikkel Strange, Kristian S. Thygesen, Tejs Vegge, Lasse Vilhelmsen, Michael Walter, Zhenhua Zeng, and Karsten W. Jacobsen. The atomic simulation environment—a Python library for working with atoms. *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 29(27):273002, 2017.
- [7] Ali Javadi-Abhari, Matthew Treinish, Kevin Krsulich, Christopher J. Wood, Jake Lishman, Julien Gacon, Simon Martiel, Paul D. Nation, Lev S. Bishop, Andrew W. Cross, Blake R. Johnson, and Jay M. Gambetta. Quantum computing with Qiskit. 2024. Version Number: 3.
- [8] Santosh Kumar, James J. C. Counter, David C. Grinter, Matthijs A. van Spronsen, Pilar Ferrer-Escorihuela, Alex Large, Marcin W. Orzech, Pawel Jerzy Wojcik, and Georg Held. An electrochemical flow cell for operando XPS and NEXAFS investigation of solid–liquid interfaces. *J. Phys. Energy*, 6(3):036001, July 2024.

- [9] Raju Lipin and Matthias Vandichel. Modeling metal electrocatalysts as cathodes: The urgent need to look beneath the surface. *ACS Energy Letters*, 10(11):5880–5884, 2025.
- [10] Jarrod R McClean, Nicholas C Rubin, Kevin J Sung, Ian D Kivlichan, Xavier Bonet-Monroig, Yudong Cao, Chengyu Dai, E Schuyler Fried, Craig Gidney, Brendan Gimby, Pranav Gokhale, Thomas Häner, Tarini Hardikar, Vojtěch Havlíček, Oscar Higgott, Cupjin Huang, Josh Izaac, Zhang Jiang, Xinle Liu, Sam McArdle, Matthew Neeley, Thomas O’Brien, Bryan O’Gorman, Isil Ozfidan, Maxwell D Radin, Jhonathan Romero, Nicolas P D Sawaya, Bruno Senjean, Kanav Setia, Sukin Sim, Damian S Steiger, Mark Steudtner, Qiming Sun, Wei Sun, Daochen Wang, Fang Zhang, and Ryan Babbush. OpenFermion: the electronic structure package for quantum computers. *Quantum Sci. Technol.*, 5(3):034014, July 2020.
- [11] Alberto Peruzzo, Jarrod McClean, Peter Shadbolt, Man-Hong Yung, Xiao-Qi Zhou, Peter J. Love, Alán Aspuru-Guzik, and Jeremy L. O’Brien. A variational eigenvalue solver on a photonic quantum processor. *Nat Commun*, 5(1):4213, July 2014.
- [12] Qiming Sun, Timothy C. Berkelbach, Nick S. Blunt, George H. Booth, Sheng Guo, Zhendong Li, Junzi Liu, James McClain, Elvira R. Sayfutyarova, Sandeep Sharma, Sebastian Wouters, and Garnet Kin-Lic Chan. The Python-based simulations of chemistry framework (PySCF). 2017.
- [13] Ming-Yu Yang and Xin-Ping Wu. Level-shifted embedded cluster method for modeling the chemistry of metal oxides. *Journal of Chemical Theory and Computation*, 20(3):1386–1397, 2024.